

Identity Realization in Bessie Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather*

Raphael Terhemba Tayol & Rhoda Andrea M. Aorabee
Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

Identity realisation has remained a major preoccupation of South African writers. African female writers mould social depictions to present a quest for their identity formation demands. For a writer like Head whose personal life and experiences bear a reasonable level of broken identity, her literature captures a burning desire to recreate, rebuild, and realize her lost identity. Using hybridity as a major strand of identity struggle in post coloniality theory, this paper evaluates Bessie Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* to decipher her ideality concerning identity creation and realisation. The paper discovers that Head's vision of identity realization is achieved as the women become key players in the success of the agricultural programme initiated by Gilbert and Makhaya Maseko. The themes of love and brotherhood are typically achieved by employing the generosity of personalities like Mma-Millipede and the relationship that exists between Makhaya and Paulina Sobeso. The women characters yearn for equality in their marital relationships, these are strong-willed women with minds of their own. The paper concludes that Head uses these themes to strengthen thoughts on reshaping fragmented lives like hers.

Key Words: Identity, hybridity, postcoloniality, relationship.

Résumé

La quête de soi est restée une préoccupation majeure chez des écrivains sud-africains. Les écrivaines africaines façonnent des représentations sociales pour présenter une quête de leurs demandes de création identitaire. Pour une écrivaine comme Head dont la vie et les expériences personnelles souffrent quelque part de son identité brisée, son œuvre littéraire capte un désir brûlant de recréer, de reconstruire et de retrouver son identité perdue. En se servant de l'hybridité comme axe majeur de la lutte identitaire dans la théorie post-coloniale, le présent article évalue *When Rain Clouds Gather* de Bessie Head pour déchiffrer son idéalité concernant la création et la quête de soi. À la lecture de l'article, l'on constate que la vision de Head de se découvrir est réalisée lorsque les femmes deviennent des acteurs clés qui contribuent au succès du programme agricole initié par Gilbert et Makhaya Maseko. Les thèmes de l'amour et de la fraternité deviennent généralement clairs à travers la générosité des personnalités comme Mma-Millipede et la relation qui existe entre Makhaya et Paulina Sobeso. Les personnages féminins aspirent à l'égalité dans leurs foyers. Ce sont des femmes de fortes personnalités qui croient en elles-mêmes. La conclusion de cet article est que Head emploie ces thèmes pour fortifier des pensées de réaménagement des vies fragmentées comme la sienne.

Mots clés: Identité, hybridité, post-colonialisme, relation.

Introduction

Literature is the mirror of life or a reflection of life's experiences generally. Apart from assuming this and many more duties, literature continues to perform the task of aiding the reconstruction of identities lost in different perspectives from different circumstances. This is the case with literatures from South Africa where experiences of apartheid -- the policy of racial segregation prevailed until the nineties in South Africa.

The word *apartheid* means "separateness" in the Afrikaans language (Wikipedia, n.p) and it describes the rigid racial division between the governing white minority population and the non-white majority population. The apartheid laws classified people according to racial groups - whites, or blacks and considered others as coloured, or people of mixed descent. The National Party of South Africa introduced apartheid as part of their campaign in the 1948 elections, and with the National Party victory, apartheid became the governing political policy for South Africa until the early 1990s.

These devastating effects have prompted writers like Nadine Gordimer, Alex La Guma, Can Themba, Es'kia Mphahlele, Dennis Brutus, Bessie Head and others to protest against the oppressions and dehumanising experiences meted against the people of South Africa, show a quest for survival and suggest a suitable identity for themselves through their writings. Bayo Ogunjimi states that "...protest, conflict, deviance, exile and struggle have been the major preoccupations of South African literature. These ... contradictions provide the search-lights for an egalitarian society devoid of racial segregation"(94). This affirms the fact that South African literature has mostly contained issues of resistance and great efforts towards identity realisation. This is occasioned by the fact that the writers are eager to draw up a new, unique, peaceful and positive personality where equality, brotherly love and an enterprising future are assured.

This paper examines how Head uses her South African experiences to create an imaginary identity for herself through her characters in *When Rain Clouds Gather*. Head is a coloured, born in an asylum's hospital in South Africa, to a white woman who was considered mad; her father was black. Head was taken from her mother at birth and raised in a foster home until the age of thirteen. She attended missionary school and eventually became a teacher. Abandoning teaching after only a few years, she began to write for the *Golden City Post*.

As the political crisis deepened in South Africa in the 1960s, Bessie went to exile in rural Botswana where she remained in refugee status for fifteen years before gaining citizenship. It is in Botswana that her literary career began to blossom.. Her writings cover many aspects of her personal experiences as a racially mixed person, growing up without a family in South Africa.

Review of Related Literature

Different scholars have asserted different views on Bessie Head's works (especially on *When Rain Clouds Gather*) and have come up with varied conclusions. Among these works is Adamu Pangmeshi's "The Utopian Quest in Bessie Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* and *Maru*". In this essay, Pangmeshi examines Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* and *Maru* from a New Historicist perspective in a bid to demonstrate that her novel has been provoked by her life in the dystopian South African history. What Pangmeshi does not

include in his research is the fact that Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* agitates a society that is in absolute quest for peace and harmony and parallels the society of South African where there was no love, trust, brotherliness and an equal room for human co-existence. An ideal or a perfect society is a figment of the imagination that Head creates in *When Rain Clouds Gather*.

Corwin Luthuli Mhlahlo also agrees with this position in his "Identity, Discrimination and Violence in Bessie Head's Trilogy". He explores the perceived intricate relationship that exists between constructed identity, discrimination and violence as portrayed in Bessie Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather*, *Maru* and *A Question of Power* from varied perspectives including aspects of coloniality, materialist feminism and liminality. His major concern is with the affinities that exist between identity, discrimination and violence. This paper agrees with Mhlahlo's disposition because he probes the possible range of identity construction especially in *When Rain Clouds Gather* given the hybrid nature of the author's experiences in South Africa and Botswana.

In her analysis of *When Rain Clouds Gather* and *Maru*, Sophia Ogwude concludes that the two novels can only be placed on a platform of Utopian literature because she weighs them on the desire of the author to create models of ideal societies where she (the author) could realize her social and self-identity (16). In a separate essay entitled "An Exile Writing on Home: Protest and Commitment in the Works of Bessie Head", Ogwude affirms that the novels of Head are socially relevant and are completely dedicated to identity renewal and personality moulding. She concludes that Head has been able to achieve this in these novels because "she is socially and politically aware, which means that she is a socially responsible writer committed [to retaining her identity and those of others who have lost their individuality]" (65). The perspective of social commitment which Ogwude raises is a reflection of Head's acknowledgment of her disfigured personal identity and a dedication to its reformation and reconstruction through the characters and their roles in *When Rain Clouds Gather*. These researches have failed to acknowledge that *When Rain Clouds Gather* is Head's attempt towards a renewal of her personality and a recreation of her disfigured identity hence the present research.

Theoretical Framework

This paper has adopted the postcolonial theory as its theoretical framework. This is because postcolonialism is the platform through which a clearer investigation on issues of identity can be achieved. This theory deals with the writing and reading of literature written in previously or currently colonized countries or literature written in colonizing countries which deals with colonization or colonized people. Notable proponents of this theory include Edward Said, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak and Homi Bhabha among others. The theory focuses particularly on the way in which literature by the colonizing culture distorts the experience and realities, and inscribes inferiority on the colonized people distorting their history and identity. It focuses on literature by the colonized people which attempts to articulate their identity and make efforts towards reclaiming their past in the face of that past's inevitable crudeness. The theory also has features such as neo-colonialism, hybridity, identity, otherness, culture and imperialism, essentialism, orientalism among others. For the

purpose of this paper, identity and hybridity' have been chosen as suitable strands for analyzing how Head advocates a new identity and personality realisation in her novel *When Rain Clouds Gather*.

According to Bill Ashcroft, construction of identity implies an endless interplay of fissions and fusions dependent on the individual's encounter and reaction to new experiences (89). Hybridity, on the other hand, emerges as the co-existence of differences. In such cases, differences meet, mix and tolerate one another. This is exemplified by characters in *When Rain Clouds Gather* who imbibe new ways which they then blend with their own and use to improve themselves. Hybridity is thus, depicted as a site for social renewal. It exposes individuals to new and progressive ideas outside their own world view. In this way, hybridity creates space for a wider understanding of mankind as well as the need to improve oneself and above all, it thrives on mutual understanding of differences.

For instance, Mma Millipede is able to grasp the religion of the missionaries and use its message to adorn and enrich her own originality of thought and expand the natural kindness of her heart. Thus, within the spaces of hybridity, difference is regarded as a resource from which all other parties can reconstruct their lives, and by extension, reconstruct their identity. This reflects the dynamism of fusion which results in a process of continuous transformation.

Synopsis of *When Rain Clouds Gather*

When Rain Clouds Gather opens at the South African border fence with Botswana. The protagonist, Makhaya Maseko, is in the process of disengaging with the past. He feels certain about his desire to leave it behind but is uncertain about the future he wishes to embrace. A young Zulu activist recently out of prison, Makhaya has defied the South African government ban order against him by fleeing the country. His one desire is to live in a free country, although he has no illusions about the quality of freedom he will enjoy in a country as miserable and poor as Botswana. After he registers as a refugee, Makhaya happens to meet Dinorego, a wise old man from Golema Mmidi, who helps him settle down into a quiet search for peace.

Dinorego and the villagers of Golema Mmidi have no concept of the deep-seated hatred that people like Makhaya have felt directed at them from whites and which they had internalized in their struggle to survive apartheid. After being ruthlessly divorced by her womanizing husband, an elderly woman –Mma Millipede sought refuge in Golema Mmidi. She, like Dinorego, exemplifies an innocent embrace of life in Botswana. She combines ancient wisdom with the Christian religion of the missionaries. The Botswana people are so secure in their own identity that foreigners and their new ideas are examined and courageously absorbed into the Botswana way of life. An Englishman, Gilbert Balfour, for example, can afford to live and dream in Golema Mmidi because of his belief that the people are open to change and to those things that promote progress. His study of agriculture is an attempt to counteract his stifling middle-class upbringing with the life-giving force of growing things. Gilbert has helped the villagers start a cooperative farming project that is yielding a good return, and his dream is to see Golema Mmidi become an internationally renowned agricultural community which helps people restore their lost personalities.

Gilbert's commitment to the land is evident in his marriage to Dinorego's daughter, the quiet but unpredictable Maria. Makhaya's timely appearance in Golema Mmidi further accelerates Gilbert's dream of a transformed economy for a people who are poor. Makhaya's philosophical rejection of tribalism and even his disillusionment with politics is appealing to Gilbert who needs someone willing to assist his efforts in the agricultural development of the village. Makhaya's task is to help the women of the village move beyond subsistence farming to cash-crop tobacco farming since their men are out of the village in faraway cattle posts at this time of the year.

Without the cooperation of the women, both Gilbert and Makhaya note that the agricultural miracle they envision will die. With the help of Mma Millipede, they enlist the young Motswana widow, Paulina Seboso, who persuades the women of the village to join the new tobacco-growing scheme. Makhaya's preoccupation with this absorbing world of innocence and growing things is alternately disrupted by the harshness of the land, the often fatal drought conditions, the painful poverty around him, and, worst of all, the African grade of evil personified in the embittered Chief Matenge and the politician Joas Tsepe. Matenge has been appointed administrator over Golema Mmidi by his brother, Chief Sekoto, who is trying to rid himself of the contentious and greedy Chief Matenge. Matenge is disliked by the villagers, for he stands in the way of progress.

Having been trained in the old school of masters and slaves, oppressor and oppressed, this traditional ruler regards the change sweeping the country as a disheartening development. Slowly he is losing his grip on power and his privileged lifestyle, and he fails in his attempts to banish Gilbert and Makhaya, whom he sees as encouraging rebellion through their zealous advocacy for change. Matenge's chief supporter, Joas Tsepe, who represents the new breed of African nationalists, is also bitter. He is part of the opposition that has lost an election and he has become a destructive force against all forms of national progress. Tsepe and Matenge become partners in criticism, connivance, and conspiracy. Matenge's continual juridical onslaught against the villagers meets with successful appeals at the higher court, where Chief Sekoto, who despises his brother, always sides with the appellants. As the chief administrator of the region, Matenge holds power over the villagers but his ruling is always subject to that of the chief. Matenge's unyielding attachment to tradition finally leads to his self-destruction, when he decides, against his better judgement, to humiliate Paulina for an unstated crime. Paulina speculates that her crime might be that she failed to inform the Chief of the funeral of her son, who died of tuberculosis at a cattle outpost. It is more likely that Matenge is simply jealous of her immense influence over the women of the village and is angry that the tobacco project has been initiated without his permission. In any case, Paulina's tragic loss of her son, Isaac, and the loss of all her cattle to the severe drought do not deter the selfish Matenge. He has also not offered any help or words of comfort to the grieving community of villagers who have suffered the loss of most of their cattle and are now looking for ways to preserve the rest of their herd through the remainder of the unpredictable drought season.

His misjudgement in summoning Paulina to court at such a critical time angers the villagers. Assembling in front of Matenge's house, they quietly wait for the Chief to declare his case against Paulina. But Matenge never makes his appearance. Barring the door to his

house, he promptly takes his own life. Makhaya is the first to discover Matenge's tragic decision.

By this time in the story, Makhaya has become a welcomed member of the community. He remains, however, a security risk, a former political prisoner who is allegedly violent, and does not know how long he will be able to maintain his place in Golema Mmidi, a village he now loves. From the many ironies and riddles he has witnessed in this remote village, he comes to the conclusion that freedom lies not in rejecting everything but in confronting life in all its contradictions. Makhaya's marriage proposal to Paulina, which she gladly accepts marks his realization that although life is harsh, its magic lies in creating a world fit to live in, rather than in succumbing to the death wish of the oppressor. In the end, Makhaya learns that a peaceful haven is not a retreat from responsibility but a place one creates through hard work, risk-taking, and involvement in the lives of others.

Identity Realisation in *When Rain Clouds Gather*

Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* is basically a novel preoccupied with Makhaya's quest for a favourable identity. To achieve this, there need to be efforts towards survival which involves advancing entrepreneurship strategies by acknowledging the significance of agricultural practices, imbibing love and brotherly trust, having faith in others, and ensuring equality and respect for human dignity. Below is an explication of these themes.

Identity Realisation as a Quest for Survival

The significance of Head's title *When Rain Clouds Gather* practically depicts identity pursuit and realization of people from different backgrounds gathered in a place suitable for their personality realizations. When rain drops on arid land, there is elation, and the perception that pervades the surroundings where rain has fallen is that of 'good things to come'. In the novel, the symbol of rain clouds depicts an assemblage of good people gathered together for the good of Golema Mmidi. People like Makhaya Maseko, Paulina Sobeso, Gilbert Balfour have left their places for Golema Mmidi in search of a reliable settings and locations where they can meet with like minds to actualize their desired dreams.

Makhaya Maseko leaves South Africa, a land where he has lived under traumata caused by oppression and the harsh realities of the apartheid regime. His intent is to "... step on free ground" (4), and by living in a free country, Makhaya believes that the evils that have twisted his life will gain desired identity. In a bid to survive the traumatic South African apartheid atmosphere of racism and revive his lost and traumatised personality, Makhaya has chosen a path – to leave an environment that was adversely or positively affecting the discovery of his inner and emotional potentials. Head further explains Makhaya's reasons for leaving South Africa as not being civilized enough to support his pursuit for personal rebirth and reawakening. In South Africa, "...he could not marry and have children ... black men were called 'boy' and 'dog' and 'kaffir'(11).

On his way out of South Africa to the station, Makhaya discovers that the atmosphere outside of the part of Africa where he had left friendly and accommodating; the little footpath leading to the dirt road where he gets a vehicle to the station is bewitchingly beautiful'(11). He could not help but say "I might like it here" (11). This

means that the surroundings of his conscience conform to his utmost desire at that time and ensure that his stay in the place he is heading to guarantees his survival.

Then, he arrives Golema Mmidi, a place in Botswana which consists mostly of people who had left their own places perhaps in search of a new identity as well. Gilbert Balfour is one of such people who had come from Britain three years before and thought it wise to return to this area again despite challenges because it aided "... his choice of career [which is] – to assist in agricultural development and improved techniques of food production" (18). Dinorego was articulating Gilbert's enthusiasm for Golema Mmidi to Makhaya and was wondering what would happen if Gilbert leaves Golema Mmidi. He also wonders "... who will pour out knowledge like rain?" (22). A spirit of fulfillment fills Makhaya's person again and he affirms the complementarities of the environment he has found for himself by saying for the second time "I might like it here" (23). This affirmation further intensifies the vital nature of the freedom which will in turn aid Makhaya and the other people like Gilbert who have come from other places seeking for survival. Makhaya Maseko and Gilbert Balfour's interpersonal conversation that strays to the end of the second chapter of the novel carries the undertone that the location in which they find themselves is well aligned with their desired future objectives thereby securing their survival.

Head affirms this when she says "... if you find a society that leaves the individual to develop freely, you ought to choose that society as your home" (82), Makhaya does this and also allows himself to be greatly influenced by his new home so that he could survive. He has met with Gilbert in an environment which he considers a utopia and is completely consumed by the possibilities he envisions from his surroundings. According to Head, "...[t]here was much more than South Africa that he [Makhaya] was running away from, and it included everything that he felt was keeping the continent of Africa at a standstill" (81). When he leaves South Africa in search of a favourable place to live his life, Makhaya does not allow himself to be overshadowed by the violent consciousness he begets from there. This means that his disposition when he leaves the South Africa is to disregard the violent condition that has pushed him out of South Africa so that it does not affect his relationship with other people. He prepares his mind to meet favourable conditions ahead and so had his choices made up with an optimistic disposition. In this regard, Meeker is cited in Habeeb and Habeeb as saying that "...survival depends upon our ability to change ourselves rather than our environment..."(505). This implies that our attitude towards the environment enhances an optimum response from it for survival. Makhaya's psychic temperaments changed from the South African violent perception to a social and liberal one to accommodate others and foster his personal development and that of others.

The Significance of Agriculture to Identity Realization in *When Rain Clouds Gather*

Golema Mmidi – the name of the village where Makhaya leaves South Africa to stay means "to grow crops" (23). Agricultural practices are seen to be a social and unifying factor in the novel. Basically, the aim of Gilbert's agricultural innovations in Golema Mmidi is to prepare a better atmosphere where life will be better perceived than how it seems. Golema Mmidi generally

... was a harsh and terrible country to live in. The great stretches of arid land completely stunned the mind, and every little green shoot that you put down into the barren earth just stood there, single, frail, shuddering, and not even a knowledge of soils or the germinating ability of seeds or modern machinery could help you to defeat this expansive ocean of desert. (119)

Despite these ecological hindrances, Gilbert still has a restoration perception (through agriculture) that there can still be a flow of milk and honey in Golema Mmidi. This is to be realized not based on abstract ideas but through personality and identity restorations of the individuals inhabiting Golema Mmidi.

His hopes were that

... one day there'd be some real family life and all the men would be back in the village again and the cattle would be right nearby behind enclosed, communally owned grazing grounds, and in summer the cattle would feed on grass that was three-feet high and dripped with dew, and some of the men might like to engage themselves entirely in the business of producing high-grade beef and others might like to turn Golema Mmidi into one of the greatest tobacco-producing areas in the country, and by that time some of the women have become so expert in the tobacco business they might like to help along or they might be a little rich and swanky by then and worry about the ladder in their new stockings or discuss their children's ailments over dainty cups of tea. (120-121)

Although this is Head's creative conception, it is also Gilbert's belief about the people that live within the environment in Golema Mmidi and what his perception about them reveals to him. He then begins to trust into their choices of concentration for his proposed agricultural restoration programme. He mostly believes in the ability of the women so much so that even Makhaya begins to buy into the idea of creating an opportunity through agriculture for the women to develop expertise in creating lucrative subsistence out of nothing from their immediate ecological surrounding. This, Gilbert does with a sense of serious unanimity, with Makhaya Maseko and the women of Golema Mmidi.

Brotherhood, Love and Trust for Identity Realisation

There is a spirit of brotherliness that breeds in Golema Mmidi as Makhaya Maseko arrives the village. To understand this notion of brotherhood and how it aids identity realisation in the novel, one must recognise the nature of the village. It is a unique place. "Golema Mmidi consisted of individuals who had fled - to escape the tragedies of life. Its name too marked it out from other villages, which were named after important chiefs or important events...It was one of the very few areas in the country where people were permanently settled on land" (17). Its inhabitants come from different social experiences and backgrounds - they are fugitives of life who have been brought together by the tragedies they have survived. They have a sense of unity not only in sharing experiences and suffering but also in sharing ideas and visions for a better future. Thus, their attitude of love and brotherliness fosters trust amongst them and encourages a firm inter-relationship which helps to rebuilds their lost identities.

The villagers of Golema Mmidi have carved an identity for themselves by forming brotherly relationships based on a common purpose: that of sharing property and carrying out subsistence duties for their survival. Such relationships are here referred to as

'brotherhood'. In Head's terms, however, 'brotherhood' must be understood in a wider context as having no limitations or boundaries, such as gender roles. Such brotherhood linkage becomes a community of people living together in one place and sharing interests which helps them remodel their lost personalities and identities.

This brotherly relationships formed by the villagers is unique and enriching. There is a bond of identity between the people of Golema Mmidi who are different in terms of colour, age, gender and political convictions. Makhaya finds this environment very exciting and interesting. Initially, for instance, he cannot understand how a white man could be a part of the community in Golema Mmidi. To his surprise, he discovers how a change of attitude and perception makes it easy to relate to Gilbert and Gilbert in turn comes to believe that Makhaya is his brother. Dinorego, an elderly member of the community, leads him into the wisdom of communal living when he says

"I have no words to describe Gilbert, son ... "[j]ust as I take you as my own son, so do I take Gilbert as my own son... since he is a white man and we Botswana do not know any white people, though some have lived here for many years. Many things caused me to have a change of mind. He can eat goat meat and sour milk porridge, which I have not known a white man eat before (22).

By these proclamations, Dinorego singularly outlines his trust for a man who does not share any lineage with the people of Golema Mmidi. Characters like Gilbert and Dinorego are set up by Head as models for brotherhood towards stability and personal recovery. What Dinorego reveals is that matters relating to race and colour have not been much of an issue in the lives of Botswanans - unlike the society from which Makhaya is fleeing. Hence, the first step of identification of the sense of belonging that is expressed through Makhaya's announcement is, "I might like it here ..." (23). Love is one theme that erupts from this brotherliness. Through Makhaya's relationship with Paulina Sobeso, Head illustrates how human relations should transcend factors such as colour, age, and gender. She criticises racial discrimination and gender roles from both Paulina and Makhaya's point of view. Through Paulina and Makhaya, Head introduces the idea of gender equality and marriage based on egalitarian principles. Makhaya and Paulina are polar opposites the relationship between the two begins with the private romantic interest that Paulina develops for Makhaya whose own life has previously been in turmoil. Makhaya had only learned how to hate and reject people due to the continuous disappointments he had faced in his life in South Africa. Now, Paulina has taught him to open up and realise "... that it [is] only people who give love and happiness" (171). Paulina's private agenda motivates her to work as hard as she can, as a leader of the women in the public sphere so as to be noticed by Makhaya.

And as the novel ends, Makhaya and Paulina get married and Makhaya's personality and identity are restored with even a new name (Mack) and his initial desire to live in a free terrain becomes real at the expense of "[s]o much [that had] happened so quickly" (199). Then "everything was ... new, and strange and beginning from scratch" (199). For his marriage to Paulie (who was formally Paulina and the surname Sobeso has now been removed because she has undergone an overhauling form of restoration) would yield a whole new form of beginning with "... babies and children" (198). This context can

be referred to as personal restoration occasioned by the total change envisaged in Golema Mmidi.

The relationship between Maria and Gilbert critically exemplifies the theme of love as well. The beginning of their relationship was initially hindered by the fact that Gilbert was still viewed by the villagers as a foreigner. Mma- Milipede was afraid of voicing out her perceived suspicion of the emotional likeness between Maria and Gilbert because “to her, Gilbert was a foreign man, and foreign men were a fearful unpredictable quantity in an otherwise predictable world” (73). As it is Head’s conception to develop these characters in the theme of love creatively, she unfolds the plot in a manner that both Maria and Gilbert overcome the obstacle put before them through love.

Faith

Throughout the novel, the characters display their potentials as people of faith and determination. They have faith in others and believe that goodness exists not only in abstraction but also in the people they find themselves with. Evidently, in her inter-relationship with the other characters we see this coming to play as the plot unfolds. They also believe in the fact that every human has value imbued in them which can transcend to others in any relationship engaged in. By this, they intuitively frown at people who have little regard for human dignity. For instance, Mma-Milipede’s discernment when she observes that “...people who err against human life ... are more blind than others to the mystery of life” (136), it means that her disposition toward life generally encourages a peaceful coordination between the people she meets not minding their race or gender.

Equality and respect for Human Dignity

The fact that Head’s characters are both male and female emphasises the nature of their connection. This enables her to define them through the promotion of individuality within any sphere or social structure. In *When Rain Clouds Gather*, the women characters - Paulina and Maria yearn for equality in their marital relationships. These are strong-willed women with minds of their own - women who do not wish to see their individuality destroyed by marriage. The male protagonists, on the other hand, are positioned by Head to understand only too well the evil that comes with oppression and discrimination. In this sense, the relationships between Paulina and Makhaya, Maria and Gilbert, Mma-Millipede and Dinorego are ideal, because they are intended to demonstrate the recognition of equality and respect for human dignity. Head is critical of women who allow themselves to be oppressed and dominated by men, “in spite of the advantage they had over men educationally few of the women developed a new personality. They remained their same old tribal selves, docile and inferior” (68). This critique is qualified by the imbalances and inconsistencies that occur even in the most egalitarian of relationships.

Head’s humanistic vision has recognised her endorsement of human equality and goodness. This is pertinent to the relationship between Maria and Gilbert. They are different in terms of race, family values and aspirations, but being human is what renders them equal. Head thus, allows us to witness the fact that issues of race, gender, and status should not stand in the way of human goodness. Minor disagreements in the Maria-Gilbert relationship must not be viewed as jeopardising the scheme of universal love and crave for human

dignity, but rather an attempt toward strengthening it. An incident in the relationship between Paulina and Makhaya can serve to reveal the same point:

“I want some tea”, he said by way of explanation. “But I will light the fire and make it.” “Goodness!” she said in alarm,... “Don't touch the fire. It's a woman's work.” “Goodness!” he said, imitating her speech. “It's time you learned that men live on this earth too. If I want to make tea, I'll make it, and if I want to sweep the floor, I'll sweep it. (145).

Makhaya agitates for equality even in roles and domestic duties. He does not ask Paulina to serve him tea, but decides to do it himself. Makhaya wants the freedom to do things that have traditionally been confined to women. Paulina is startled by this sudden take-over of her role –“it's a woman's work”. Yet the custom that “men have always had their way” must be balanced with what the modern liberated women want: equal opportunity with their male counterparts. Therefore, Makhaya seeks a similar chance in what is considered women's work. Head also agitates for the realization of the fact that human relationships should be balanced and should not thrive on the disadvantage of others. She designs a conversation which illustrates Paulina's observation of Makhaya's fire-making:

Paulina watched the fire-making with a critical eye, and it occurred to her for the first time why the ancestors had set certain jobs aside for women and certain jobs for men. Men and women were unlike mentally. Look at how this man built a fire! He treated each stick as a separate living entity and because of his respect for each stick, he moved his hands slowly with many pauses, placing the firewood down at carefully calculated angles. This fire was set for a limited purpose it was meant to boil water for tea and bum beautifully without smoke.... A woman worked differently. She grasped a bunch of sticks in her hand, but it wasn't the tea only but a thousand other purposes that fire would serve.... (146)

Through Paulina and Makhaya, Head suggests different approaches to the fulfilment of similar duties. Makhaya's approach is aesthetic: he is artistic and calculating in his manner of doing things. The fire he makes is perfect, beautiful and devoid of smoke. Makhaya does not merely make a fire, he creates it: the fire represents the ideal fire, “smokeless and bright”(147). By contrast, Paulina cannot manage such precision. She is a pragmatist. She does things for practical reasons rather than for beauty. As a woman, Paulina fills numerous roles; it seems pointless to her to waste her time on aesthetics when people are hungry. For her, the fire must fulfil a number of functions and not just neatly boil water for tea. The same fire must enable her to cook, heat water, warm the house and iron clothes. Her view of the fire is utilitarian: it must be useful rather than decorative.

In this novel, Head identifies with the downtrodden, people with no identity. What she professes to like are human simplicity and ordinariness. In other words, Head is explaining her preference for not finding a model of identity in powerful people or in structures of power. She believes in humanity, in humaneness and in humanitarianism. By virtue of her uncertain origins she claims the identity of the poor and the Botswanans are models in this regard. In her writing, one can see the gradual process of her association and sharing with the Botswana within which Head's quest for an identity is realised.

Conclusion

Much of what Head identifies with in *When Rain Clouds Gather* is a total commitment to the significance and the value of life and how it can and always changes human existential components. The theme of survival, that of the importance of agriculture, the theme of brotherhood, all go to intensify Head's concern for the value and pursuit for a positive identity. Head uses the theme of love to also strengthen our thoughts on the power that love has in reshaping our fragmented lives. The love between Maria and Gilbert has been able to build trust which was not developed by the people of Golema Mmidi on a foreigner. Makhaya's love affair with Paulina has changed Makhaya from viciousness to an open person who relates well and accepts people the way they are and work with them. He is emotionally forced out of his dead conscience to a positive thinker.

The experiences of both Makhaya Maseko and Gilbert Balfour carefully put together by Head demonstrate that personal identity restoration draws a great deal from the brotherliness and togetherness in activities like agriculture. Just as Simon Estok establishes the importance of 'place' in his analysis of *As for Me and My House*, it is evident even in any form of analysis of *When Rain Clouds Gather* that the place of Golema Mmidi was a place for restoration of personality, identity, vision mission and of total rehabilitation for a whole new, strange but overwhelming actualisation and accomplishment of one's dreams in life. The likes of Paulina Sobeso, Makhaya Maseko are key testimonies to this.

Works Cited

- Ashcroft, Bill. "Worldliness." *Horizons in Post-Colonial Studies: Edward Said and the Postcolonial*. Eds. Bill Ashcroft and Hussein Kadhim. Huntington: Nova Science Publishers, Inc., 2001. Web.
- Estok, Simon. "An Ecocritical Reading of Slightly Queer's *As for Me and My House*." *Journal of Canadian Studies*. 44.3 (2010): 75-93. Web.
- Habeeb, Gulfishaan, and Durafshaan Habeeb. "Eco-Critical Theory or E-Theory: Some Newer Perspectives." *Proceedings of National Seminar on Postmodern Literary Theory and Literature*, 2012. 504-507. Web.
- Head, Bessie. *When Rain Clouds Gather*. London: Heinemann, 1969. Print
- Corwin Luthuli. "Identity, Discrimination and Violence in Bessie Head's Trilogy". Diss. University of South Africa, 2002. Print.
- Ogunjimi, Bayo. "Literature and National Development." *Major Themes in African Literature*. Eds. Damian Opata and Ohaegbu Aloysius. Nsukka: AP Pub. Com., 2009. 85-100. Web.
- Ogwude, Sophia *Bessie Head: An Exile Writing on Home*. Zaria: A.B.U. Press Ltd, 1998. Print.
- . "An Exile Writing on Home: Protest and Commitment in the Works of Bessie Head." *Exile and African Literature*. Eds. Durosimi, Jones and Marjorie Jones. Oxford: African Word Press, 2000. Print.
- Pangmeshi, Adamu. "The Utopian Quest in Bessie Head's *When Rain Clouds Gather* and *Maru*" *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*. 1,1(2009): 60-75. Print.